

IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF IDEAL-IDEOLOGICAL EDUCATION OF YOUTH

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Annotation. the article talks about the scientific and theoretical aspects of educating of young people. Factors affecting the process of ideal and ideological education have been analyzed

Key words: Idea, youth, ideology, spirituality, ideological education, ideological process, education.

The goal of any ideological education is to ensure the educational level of every member of society and every social stratum and group represented by them. As a result, it ensures that every citizen consciously adopts advanced ideas that stimulate the development of that society, turning them into his way of mind and thinking. Ideological education is a process aimed at forming the worldview of a person, social group, nation, society, arming them with ideological knowledge that expresses certain goals. This aspect is one of the main features of ideological education. Ideological education is manifested first of all in virtues such as high faith, responsibility for the Motherland and the people, patriotism, self-sacrifice. The education of healthy ideas means the education of a high outlook and faith. The new worldview that was formed during the years of independence implies loyalty to the Motherland, love for national values and traditions, kindness to loved ones, loyalty to the chosen profession, idea and faith. New thinking and new mind are the product of the national consciousness, worldview and faith, which has been educated and refined in the spirit of the ideology of independence.

The concept of the means of educating the young generation in the spirit of idealism that affects the human mind, sets and changes his worldview, way of thinking, the spiritual and material foundations, traditions, values, cultural and spiritual heritage, lifestyle, ideological factors, ideas and views specific to the society, nation represents a set of dependent influence objects.

Its essence is deeply and comprehensively explained in the book "High Spirituality - Invincible Power" by First President I.A. Karimov. Based on this work, the criteria of ideological education can be conditionally divided into several groups: the first group - history covering nation, people, statehood, culture, architectural monuments, etc., agrarian cultural traditions that have been developing for thousands of years, geographical material heritage representing historical relations related to conditions; the second group is the cultural heritage, which covers several thousand years of religious faith, education, as well as all fields of science and thinkers who played an important role in their development and their works, national creativity; the third group - traditions, customs, rituals, holidays, other cultural factors related to the way of life of our people; the fourth group is people's values, way of thinking, people's ideological features, mentality and mutual social relations; the fifth group - educational institutions, mass media, libraries, theaters, art palaces, and other such

ideological institutions that have a direct practical activity in our current society, have a great influence on human education, and generally play a leading role in the formation of the ideological worldview includes educational tools.

The issue of the ideological education of the young generation is specific to every era and society, and the purpose of this is to thoroughly analyze all the factors and criteria that shape and influence responsibility before the state and society, and in order understand better their place in this regard. It is impossible to imagine any people or nation without its history, unique customs and traditions, life values. In this regard, of course, spiritual heritage, cultural assets, old historical monuments serve as the most important factors. For example, great people, scientists, scholars, politicians and generals who have grown up from this land, the services of the great scholars who were born and raised in our motherland in the rise of the secular and religious sciences, especially the knowledge related to the religion of Islam, which have become an integral part of the universal civilization and culture, to the highest level in history.

The complex constructions built on this ancient soil in the period before Christ and after, the relics that still preserve their beauty and freshness testify to the highly developed culture of agriculture and handicrafts, architecture and urban planning in our country since ancient times, and there are more than four thousand material monuments existing in the territory of our country -the fact that the ideological monument was included in the UNESCO list as a unique example of world heritage also confirms this opinion. Such immortal works of art testify to the existence of a great culture in this ancient country, in the soil where we live today, and, of course, draw our attention to the powerful influence it had in shaping the world of ideas of man is involved.

In ideological education, folk plays an important role, it shows the identity of our nation, it is passed down from generation to generation, it survives the storms of history, life and death tests, represents the noble virtues of our nation, which has survived the tests of life and death and has always preserved its identity, such as tolerance, perseverance, nobility, faithfulness and loyalty. Herewith, the importance of our holy religion, which is one of the criteria for the ideological education of the young generation, is non-comparative. Religion, as a component of human spirituality, is an integrated system of ideas and views that embodies the high ideals of mankind, the dreams of truth and truth, honesty and justice, and strengthens them in the form of stable rules.

Every scientific innovation, created discovery gives impetus to a new thought and worldview, has a unique effect on the formation of criteria for the ideological education of the young generation. From this point of view, it should be noted with pride that the exemplary life and activity of our great scientists and thinkers, as well as the unique scientific and creative discoveries of our great scholars, who lived on our land, amaze the people of the world even today. The society uses the thinkers, religion and discoveries, enlightenment, science and culture of its land to prove how rich and colorful the intellectual world of our people is, which combines all of these, and to show it as an example. It is a duty and a liability for everyone, first of all, for intellectuals, for the entire public to thoroughly study such a unique and priceless wealth in every way, to convey its meaning to the next generation.

Undoubtedly, the role and influence of the family is non-comparable in the formation and promotion of the unique ideology of any nation. Because the purest and purest feelings of a person, the first concepts and imaginations of life are formed, first of all, in the bosom of the

family. It is natural that the foundations of the ideological criteria and views that determine the child's character, nature and worldview - goodness and charity, nobility and kindness, honor and dignity - are settled in the family environment. That is why respect for parents, which appears in the family environment, and a deep understanding of the lifelong duty to them, is the basis of human qualities and family relations, the ideological basis of the family.

When it comes to the criteria of ideological education of the young generation, it is necessary to dwell on the role and influence of the neighborhood. It is known that Uzbek neighborhoods have been a place of truly national values since time immemorial. Mutual kindness, harmony and peaceful, receiving information from those in need and needing help, taking care of orphans and widows, sharing weddings, festivals and events with many people, even on a good day, customs and traditions typical of our people, such as being together even on a bad day, were first of all formed and developed in the environment of the neighborhood.

Another criterion of ideological education is science, education which are regarded as the most basic condition and guarantee of human perfection and the development of the nation. The foundations of the future are created in the schools of knowledge, in other words, the future of the nation depends on the education and upbringing of the children today. Therefore, every parent, teacher, and coach must first of all see a person in the person of each child.

So, based on this simple requirement, the main goal and task of the education sector is to raise children to become full-fledged people who have independent and broad thinking skills, who live consciously. This requires that education and upbringing work be carried out harmoniously. In ideological and moral education, no one should be left out, but the family, neighborhood, and educational institutions shall unite their forces.

An active attitude to existing ideas in society, education of an active life position is another important goal of ideology. Ideological education is the basis of moral, political and legal education. Any moral, political, legal education is aimed at protecting, promoting and developing a specific idea. In particular, the ideological goal of stressing the stability of society is hidden in feature films aimed at corrupting young people morally by promoting evil, lewdness, and cruelty. Most young viewers, who have not yet formed their minds, often learn about various evil, savagery, cruelty from such films. As a result, they become cruel, and they don't even realize that their hearts are filled with illness (vices) such as stubbornness, violence, and immorality. One even does not understand what blindly imitating the characters of such shows and films can lead sad consequences will be caused by imitating under the influence of interpretations.

Therefore, ideas can be promoted straightly or hidden, directly or indirectly, directly or symbolically. Human activity is directed towards a specific ideological goal, and this intention is often not visible, the main goal of ideological education is to create a sense of vigilance and sensitivity in people, and to form the ability to resist foreign and harmful ideas.

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